

IPBES Nature Futures Framework

Systematic literature search

Data management report

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Author: Tanya Lazarova (ORCID: 0000-0003-4337-2296)

Project members: Machteld Schoolenberg (ORCID: 0000-0002-8940-0291), Sana Okayasu, Claire Jacobs, Angelique Vermeer

Organization: PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency

Contact email: tsu-ipbes.scenarios@pbl.nl

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Preamble

The aim of the systematic literature search is to provide an overview of the literature which directly uses or mentions the IPBES Nature Futures Framework (NFF), which was developed by the former IPBES scenarios and models expert group and current IPBES task force on scenarios and models. The results of the search aim to provide an indication of the uptake of the Nature Futures Framework by the scientific community up to the IPBES Plenary at its 10th session.

The literature found through the 3 search steps are available in a public library on Zotero in the folders 'Literature which uses the NFF' and 'Literature which mentions the NFF': https://www.zotero.org/groups/4937409/nature_futures_framework/library. The folders 'Events on the NFF organized by/with TSU scenarios and models' and 'Other events related to the NFF' contain items which were collected based on the expert knowledge of the task force on scenarios and models.

This is an update of the first systematic literature search on the Nature Futures Framework conducted on 21 March 2022 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396543>).

Step 1: Systematic search on the Web of Science

The following query was used on Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>) on 20 March 2023:

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ALL=("Nature Future Framework" OR "Natures Futures Framework" OR  
"Nature Futures Framework" OR ("Nature" AND "Futures Framework"))
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Overall the search yielded 18 items, 15 of which were relevant for our purpose (either use or mention the Nature Futures Framework). Out of those 15, 10 were already identified in the earlier version of this search, and 5 were new.

Furthermore, we looked through the 40 citations of one of the core papers on the Nature Futures Framework, which was yielded by the aforementioned search (Pereira et al. 2020) and found 23 articles which were relevant for our purpose. 17 of those were already found through previous searches and 6 of those were new.

Step 2: Search on Google Scholar

The following query was used in Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>) on 23 March 2023:

"Nature Futures Framework"

The search yielded 182 records, 80 of which were relevant for our purpose (either use or mention the Nature Futures Framework). Out of those 80, we found 29 new publications, which we did not find through the Web of Science search described above or the March 2021 search.

Step 3: Expert Network

There were 5 publications sent to us by task force members, or the TSU was aware of them already, which did not appear in any of the systematic searches (Last entry 30 March 2023).

Altogether, 39 new publications were found since the last search in March 2022.

The library will be continuously updated as more input is provided by the IPBES task force on scenarios and models and the general public.